

Analytical Applications of Phenylhydrazine Sulphinic Acid for Determination of Molybdenum and Copper

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A rapid spectrophotometric method for the determination of trace amounts of molybdenum has been developed using phenylhydrazine sulphinic acid. An aqueous solution of the reagent develops a red colour with molybdate ions in acetic acid media ranging from 10 to 70% by volume. The intense red colour produced has its maximum absorbance at 510 nm. Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reaction is $0.012 \mu\text{g}$ of molybdenum cm^{-1} . The system conforms to Beer's law over the concentration range of 0.6 to 6 μg per ml of molybdenum and has a molar absorptivity of 8.0×10^3 litre $\text{mole}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$. Investigations have indicated that the reagent is a useful alternative for sulphurous acid in the determination of copper as copper(I)-thiocyanate.

PHENYLHYDRAZINE sulphinic acid was first prepared by Michaelis by the action of sulphur dioxide on phenylhydrazine¹. However, no systematic studies have been made on the analytical usefulness of this reagent. Recently it has been applied for the gravimetric determination of selenium and tellurium². In the present communication, the results of the possible use of the reagent in the quantitative determination of molybdenum and copper have been described.

Experimental

Spectrophotometric Determination of Molybdenum :

A number of reagents have been employed for the colorimetric determination of molybdenum^{3,4}. None of the organic reagents used so far, however, seems to possess any advantage over the thiocyanate method. An aqueous solution of phenylhydrazine sulphinic acid developed a red colour with molybdate ions in acetic acid media ranging from 10 to 70% by volume. The intense red colour produced has its maximum absorbance at 510 nm and conforms to Beer's law. The colour is stable for at least 60 hrs.

All the chemicals used were of analytical purity.

Standard Molybdenum Solution (0.01M) : A standard solution was prepared by dissolving 1.839 g ammonium molybdate (Reanal, Hungary, $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$) per litre and standardised gravimetrically using 8-hydroxyquinoline⁵. Working solutions of molybdenum were prepared by dilution.

Preparation and Properties of the Reagent : Phenylhydrazine sulphinic acid was prepared by the action of sulphur dioxide on an ethereal solution of phenylhydrazine. The reagent is a white crystalline compound and is freely soluble in water, alcohol and acetone, yield, 80%. On gentle heating phenylhydrazine sulphinic acid loses a molecule of water forming sulphur yellow thionyl phenylhydrazine¹.

Reagent Solution : A 4% (w./v.) solution of the reagent in water was employed.

Apparatus : An ECL Spectrophotometer Model GS 866 was employed for photometric measurements.

Recommended Procedure : To an aliquot of the molybdenum solution containing 0.05 to 0.15 mg molybdenum, 10 ml of acetic acid (sp. gr. 1.048) and 5 ml of reagent solution were added. The solution was warmed on a hot plate for 10 min. After cooling to room temperature it was transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask and diluted to volume with water. The photometric measurement was made at 510 nm using water as blank. The molybdenum concentration was read from the calibration graph prepared by using standards containing 0.015-0.15 mg molybdenum.

Determination of Copper :

Phenylhydrazine sulphinic acid had recently been used for the gravimetric determination of tellurium by the authors². Investigations have indicated that the reagent is a useful alternative for sulphurous acid in the determination of copper as copper(I)-thiocyanate.

An aliquot (100 ml) of standard copper solution (1 ml = 1 mg) was taken in a beaker and the volume was diluted to 200 ml. To this was added 25 ml of 4% reagent solution and few drops of hydrochloric acid. This was heated to boiling and a freshly prepared 5 ml of 10% ammonium thiocyanate solution was added with constant stirring. An excess of thiocyanate reagent up to 20 ml caused no harm to the determination. This was digested for 20 min on a water bath and was allowed to settle for 30 min. It was immediately filtered through a weighed crucible of G-4 porosity, washed, dried and weighed. The accuracy and precision of the method are both within 0.1%.

Results and Discussion

The conditions were established after the following factors affecting the reaction were investigated.

Acidity and Reagent Concentration: If the concentration of acetic acid lies between 10 to 70% by volume, the wavelength of maximum absorption and the absorbance value remain unchanged. For the sake of uniformity in operation, an intermediate concentration of 40% by volume was selected. To known aliquot of molybdenum, varying amounts of the reagent were added and the colour developed with acetic acid. The study indicated that the maximum colour formation a 0.1 g of the reagent should be used. Higher reagent concentrations up to 0.4 g showed no improvement in the colour intensity. In practice, for every 0.15 mg of molybdenum 0.2 g of the reagent was used. The reagent does not absorb at the wavelength for maximum absorbance for the coloured product.

Time of Digestion: The digestion was done for times varying from 3 to 15 min. The colour formation was complete within 5 to 10 min and a time of 10 min is therefore recommended.

Molar Absorptivity, Sensitivity and Optimum Concentration: The molar absorptivity of the colour system at 510 nm was found to be 8.0×10^3 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ calculated on the basis of molybdenum. The sensitivity of the colour reaction was 0.012 μ g of molybdenum cm² $\times$ (Sandell's nomenclature). The system conforms to Beer's law between 0.015 to 0.15 mg of molybdenum per 25 ml.

Interference Study: In order to assess possible analytical applications of the reaction, the effects of some ions which often accompany molybdenum were studied. Different amounts of ionic species were added to 150 μ g of molybdenum solution in

25 ml volumetric flasks and the colour was developed using 10 ml acetic acid and 5 ml reagent solution. The tolerance limits for various ions are shown in Table 1. When barium was present the solution was centrifuged before colour measurement. Oxalate and tartrate interfered.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF DIVERSE IONS ON THE DETERMINATION OF MOLYBDENUM (Amount of Mo (VI) TAKEN :—6 ppm.

Ion added	Tolerance limit ppm.	Ion added	Tolerance limit ppm.
Fe(II)	250	Ce(IV)	150
Fe(III)	300	Th(IV)	120
Mn(II)	220	UO ₂ (II)	100
Zn(II)	350	Be(II)	40
Cd(II)	150	Cr(III)	20
Ni(II)	250	tungstate	20
Ba(II)	150	vanadate	100
Ca(II)	200	arsenate	200
Sr(II)	200	phosphate	250
Mg(II)	200	chloride	500
Sb(III)	250	sulphate	450
Tl(III)	120	nitrate	250
Zr(IV)	100		

Conclusions: Phenylhydrazine sulphinic acid compares well with the most sensitive and widely used reagents for the spectrophotometric determination of molybdenum. The method is rapid, simple and the produced colour is sufficiently stable. The reagent does not absorb at the wavelength for maximum absorbance for the coloured system.

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